

TOPICAL COCOA APPLICATION AS A PROTECTIVE AGENT AGAINST SKIN CANCER DUE TO THE EXPOSURE OF 7,12-DIMETHYLBENZEN (A) ANTHRACENE (DMBA) IN CORRELATION WITH MELONDYALDEHYDE (MDA), AND EXPRESSION OF BCL 2

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Skin cancer is one type of cancer which the number of the patient increases from year to year. Cocoa has powerful antioxidant content, such as flavonoids, catechins, epicatechin and proanthocyanidin, which in a previous study showed protective effects against cancer. Carcinogenic agents induce the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which damage DNA, RNA and reacted with fatty acids in the cell membrane then forming malondialdehyde (MDA) at the initiation phase. In malignancy, the excessive expression of Bcl-2 can be found as one of the initiation phases of carcinogenesis.

Objective: To determine the differences in MDA levels, Bcl-2 tissue expression between control mice and mice that applied DMBA and topical cocoa extract with different concentrations.

Method: The study sample was 30 Swiss albino mice, divided into six groups of 5 mice each: Group I without treatment, group II DMBA, III cacao 200 ppm and DMBA, IV cocoa 400 ppm and DMBA, V cocoa 800 ppm. The cocoa extract was applied every day followed by DMBA with 1-day interval, all for one week.

Result: In the experiment group, the lowest level of MDA is in the 200 ppm cocoa group ($p \leq 0.05$). MDA level is increasing along with cocoa concentration; however, at the highest cocoa concentration 800 ppm, the average of MDA level is still lower than the DMBA group. Bcl-2 expression was shown in 60% of the subjects in the DMBA group, 40% of the subjects in the 200 ppm cocoa group, 20% in the 400 ppm and 800 ppm cocoa group.

Conclusion: Topical application of cocoa extract has a protective effect in the initiation phase because there is a decrease in MDA levels at a concentration of 200 ppm. The expression of Bcl-2 decreased along with the increasing concentration of cocoa extract.

KEYWORDS Cocoa extract, Bcl-2, DMBA, MDA

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Introduction

Skin cancer is one type of cancer which the number of sufferers increases from year to year. It is estimated that the incidence of skin cancer reaches 2-4% of the number of cancer patients. [1] In Indonesia, the official data of the prevalence of skin cancer do not yet exist, data in South Sulawesi at Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital, Makassar, the number of patients with skin cancer in 2009 was 126 people. In Cipto Mangunkusumo Hospital in 2005, patients with skin cancer, 47.4% were male, and 52.6% were female. [2] Cacao is a natural substance that has powerful antioxidant content, such as flavonoids, catechins, epicatechin and proanthocyanidin. Research showed that epicatechin is a strong inhibitor on plasma lipid peroxidase because polyphenols bind to low-density lipoprotein. [3] Jourdain et al., 2008 showed that cocoa polyphenol extract with the concentration of 0.001-0.2% could inhibit the growth of metastatic and non-metastatic cancer cells in prostate cancer cells. [4] Cocoa has an anti-proliferative effect through its ability to decrease the extracellular regulated kinase, protein kinase B and cyclin D1 along with the pro-apoptotic effect which proven by the decrease of Bcl-xL level and an increase in BAX level and caspase-3 activity. [5]

Carcinogenesis of skin cancer occurs through 3 stages; initiation, promotion and progression. One of the chemicals known to induce the carcinogenesis stage is 7,12-dimethylbenz (A) anthracene (DMBA) as the initiator. [6] The application of carcinogenic agent induces the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) which damages DNA, RNA and protein [7] through chemical reactions such as oxidation, nitration and halogenation which cause mutations, changes in the function of important proteins and enzymes. [8] ROS reacts with fatty acids in the cell membrane, then forming lipid peroxidase and malondialdehyde (MDA). [9] If the DNA damages could not be repaired, apoptosis occurred. The process of apoptosis through 2 pathways, they are extrinsic or cytoplasmic and the intrinsic or mitochondrial pathway which causes cytochrome C release from mitochondria. [10,11] The intrinsic pathway regulator is Bcl-2. [12] The excessive expression of Bcl-2 can be found in many cases of malignancy, even without chromosome translocation (Kr 18.14). [1] The protective effect of cocoa extract related to the formation of skin cancer is not yet known. Therefore, this study aims to assess MDA and Bcl-2 expression in epithelial tissue at the initiation stage of carcinogenesis.

Material and Methods

This study is a true experiment post-test design with a control group, conducted in the Animal Laboratory of Veterinary Faculty, Hasanuddin University. There was the previous study which examined the effects of DMBA. 50 mg of DMBA was given three times a week for only one week then obtained histopathological changes such as dysplasia and squamous cell carcinoma. The cocoa extract was made from 500 grams of cocoa using the soxhation method; the sample was extracted with 96% ethanol.

Liquid extract of ethanol was rotavaporated then stored in the excavator until the water evaporated and absorbed in silica gel. After dried, the extract was diluted to the concentration of 200 ppm, 400 ppm, 800 ppm.

The research subject was Swiss albino mice, female, age 6-9 weeks, obtained from the Maros Balitbang Veterinary centre. The

mice were from the same parent. The weight was about 15-25 g. The sample is excluded if it sick or die during the experiment. There were 30 samples, divided into six groups of 5 mice each: Group I without treatment, group II DMBA, III cocoa 200 ppm and DMBA, cocoa IV 400 ppm and DMBA, V cocoa 800 ppm and DMBA. The cocoa extract was applied every day, followed by DMBA with one-day interval, all for one week. Mice were photographed at the beginning and during the study. DMBA and cocoa applications were applied on shaved backs. Twenty-four hours after the last application of DMBA, all the mice were checked for MDA and Bcl-2.

Immunohistochemistry and MDA examinations were conducted in the Microbiology Laboratory of Hasanuddin University Hospital. Data obtained from MDA examination were statistically analyzed using ANOVA, data on Bcl-2 expression were analyzed using the Kruskal Wallis test.

Results

Level of total flavonoids and polyphenols were obtained, where the highest level was at the concentration of 800 ppm with 59.36 µg and 33.12 mg, while the lowest level was at the concentration of 200 ppm with total flavonoids and polyphenols were 14.48 µg and 8.28 mg.

The effect of DMBA application 3 times a week in various treatment groups showed the highest MDA levels were in the control group with 6.866±2.512, the lowest was in the negative control of 1.165 ± 1.338, the MDA level was increased along with the increasing concentration of cocoa where the highest level was in 800 ppm cocoa group with 4.843±3.188, even the highest cocoa concentration of 800 ppm MDA is still lower than the average DMBA group. The difference showed that it was statistically significant $p \leq 0.05$. Bcl-2 +1 expression was shown in 60% of the subjects in the DMBA group, 40% in the 200 ppm cocoa group was +1, 20% subjects were Bcl-2 +1 in the 400 ppm and 800 ppm cocoa group.

Discussion

The level of MDA was used to determine the level of oxidative stress induced by DMBA application in mice. The results of the ELISA examination showed that DMBA induces oxidative stress in the group the level is higher than the negative control group. The lower MDA level of the cocoa group indicates that cocoa can inhibit the formation of oxidative stress. The results of the ANOVA test showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

The application of cocoa extract before the application prooxidative DMBA showed its ability to inhibit the oxidative stress with the best protective effects at concentrations of 200 ppm and is not dose dependent. This is consistent with a study by Martin et al., 2008 showing the initial therapy of cocoa extract before the application of prooxidative tetrabutylhydroperoxide to liver cells HepG2 has been shown to prevent over oxidative stress production and prevent the reduction of the antioxidant glutathione enzyme. [13] However, the maximum effect was at the concentration of 200 ppm may be caused by the concentration of cocoa extract used in this study was too high so that an increase in the dosage of cocoa extract did not increase the effect.

From graph II, the results of the study showed the expression of Bcl-2 DMBA groups higher than the group that received cocoa so DBMA can be proven to induce Bcl-2. The expression of Bcl-2 decreases with the increasing concentration of cocoa extract. 40% of the subjects in the 200 cocoa group ppm were Bcl-2 +1, 20% in

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the 400 ppm and 800 ppm cocoa group were +1. This indicates a tendency that cocoa extract inhibits the expression of Bcl-2. The best ability to induce apoptosis seems to occur in the 800 ppm cocoa group, seen in this group having high MDA levels as a marker of high oxidative stress, but not triggering an increase in Bcl-2 expression. However, further research is needed to estimate the levels of BAX to confirm this data. By previous studies that cocoa has a pro-apoptotic effect through Bcl-2 down-regulation. [14] The effect of pro-apoptotic is determined by a positive ratio between BAX and Bcl-2, then induces the release of cytochrome-C from mitochondria, which is a determinant of the occurrence of apoptosis. [15] The statistical analysis of the treatment group showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) so that the cacao group were not proven statistically able to inhibit the expression of Bcl-2. This was happened due to the small number of samples, moreover, in this study, BAX was not specifically examined.

Conclusion

The topical application of cocoa extract before the exposure of DMBA in albino mice had the protective effect against skin cancer through the oxidative stress inhibition at the initiation phase, based on the result that the level of MDA at skin tissue in the protective group of the cocoa extract is lower than the control. The expression of Bcl-2 skin tissue in the protective group of cocoa extract decreased with the increasing cocoa concentration compared to the control group.

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Competing Interests

None

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References

1. Gloster HM NK. Skin cancer in skin of color. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2006; 55: 741–60.
2. Djawad K. Protective effects of curcumin on the formation of CPD and 8-OHdG after UVB application. In: *Post-graduate of Hasanuddin University, Makassar.* 2008.
3. JA V. Chocolate Is a Powerful ex Vivo and in Vivo Antioxidant, an Anti-Sclerotic Agent in Animal Model, and a Significant Contributor to Antioxidants in the European and American Diets. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2006; 54: 8071–6.
4. Jourdain C, Tenca G DA. In vitro effects of polyphenols from cocoa and beta-testosterone of human prostate cancer and normal cells. *Eur J Cancer Prev.* 2006; 15 (4): 353–61.
5. Romiro IR, Ramos SO EL. Cocoa-rich diet prevents azoxymethane-induced colonic prenatal elastic lesions by restraining oxidative stress and cell proliferation and inducing apoptosis. *Mol Nutr.* 2011; 55 (12): 1895–9.
6. Meeran, BC, Vaid, M., Punathil, T & K. Katiyar S. Skin Tumors Promotion 7, 12-dimethylbenz (α) anthracene in Mouse Skin, Which is Associated with the Inhibition of Inflammatory. 2009; 30 (500): 9.
7. Lin CG. Oxidative damage to RNA: mechanisms, consequences, and diseases. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2011; 67 (11): 1817–29.
8. Birben E, Sahiner UM, Sackesen C, Erzurum S, Kalayci O. Oxidative Stress and Antioxidant Defense. 2012; (January): 9–19.
9. Grigorov B. Reactive Oxygen Species and Their Relation to Carcinogenesis. *Trakia J Sci.* 2012; 10 (3): 83–92.
10. Gupta S, Kass GEN, Szegezdi E, Joseph B, Momp R. The mitochondrial death pathway: a promising therapeutic target in diseases. *J Cell Mol Med.* 2009; 13 (6): 1004–33.
11. Wang C, Youle RJ. The Role of Mitochondria in Apoptosis. 2016; 95-118.
12. Aaron N. Hata, Jeffrey A. Engelman ACF. The BCL-2 family: key mediators of the apoptotic response to targeted anti-cancer therapeutics. *Cancer Discov.* 2016; 5 (5): 475–87.
13. Martin MA, Serrano ABG Hospital. Protection of Human HepG2 Cells against Oxidative Stress by Cocoa Phenolic Extract. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2008; 56: 7765–72.
14. Andujar I, Recio MC, Giner RM RJ. Cocoa polyphenols and their potential benefits for human health. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* 2012; 2012: 1–24.
15. Min H Kang CPR. Bcl-2 Inhibitors: Targeting Mitochondrial Apoptotic Pathways in Cancer Therapy. 2011; 15 (4): 1126–32.